

QUANTIFYING MASKING IN MULTI-TRACK RECORDINGS

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ABSTRACT

It is known that one of the most important tasks in music post-production is equalization. Equalization can be applied in several ways, but one of the main purposes it serves is masking minimization. This is done so that the listener can appreciate the timbral qualities of all instruments within a musical mix. However, the study of masking between the different instruments of a multi-track mix has not received a lot of attention, and a quantitative measure based on perceptual studies has not yet been proposed. This paper presents such a measure, along with a study of masking between several common instruments. The measure proposed (cross-adaptive signal-to-masker ratio) is intended to serve as an analysis tool to be used by audio engineers when trying to combat masking using their preferred equalization techniques.

1. INTRODUCTION

Computers are being used to perform complex tasks that are inherently human and with a high degree of accuracy. Some examples of this are speech recognition [1] and automatic musical genre classification [2]. Recently, the possibility of a computer being able to down-mix a multi-track recording like an audio engineer is starting to be explored [3,4,5], and although the use of perceptual models has not been exploited for this purpose, it is the authors opinion that using computational models of perception might prove useful, if not indispensable, to achieve good results. The underlying complexities and non-linearities involved in the process of down-mixing are numerous, mainly because multi-track down mixing is a task where both technology and creativity co-exist in equal proportions so an exact set of rules for mixing does not really exist. In order for automatic down-mixing to become feasible many individual issues need to be tackled, for example, automatic panning, automatic dynamics control and automatic equalization. This work is a step towards the latter.

1.1 Masking within a musical context

When mixing a song, most of the decisions of an audio engineer are influenced by context; the genre of the music, the intended audience and for all we know even the

weather at the time of mixing can influence the engineer. Nevertheless there is one aspect of a mix that is crucial and for which most audio engineers share the same view. This is masking. Masking has been defined as the process by which the threshold of audibility for one sound is raised by the presence of another (masking) sound. Also, as the amount by which the threshold of audibility of a sound is raised by the presence of another (masking) sound. The unit customarily used is the decibel [6].

However, when talking in terms of a musical mix, the term attains a quite different definition, namely; when one signal competes with another, reducing the hearing systems ability to fully hear the desired signal, masking has occurred [7]. The latter definition emphasizes the fact that in a multi-track mix several instruments are fighting to be heard, so the ability to fully hear every individual instrument is reduced. Accordingly, when there is a lot of masking going on between the different tracks of a multi-track recording, the resulting mix is cloudy and confusing. On the other hand, an unmasked mix is the one where all the instruments are clearly defined thus allowing the listener to fully appreciate their timbral characteristics. As such, it is the authors opinion that masking minimization should be one of the pillars of an automatic mixing system.

Luckily, masking minimization is not a mystery; it is known that audio engineers employ three weapons when combating masking: setting the relative levels of tracks appropriately (thus giving priority to some of them), panning the tracks with similar content to opposite sides of the stereo panorama, and equalization to ensure that each track is allocated a portion of the spectrum.

1.2 Motivation behind this work

It is clear that there is a lot of ground to be covered in terms of studying the factors that influence the engineers decisions when performing the three steps mentioned above. For example, if an audio engineer is using the techniques to combat masking, an analysis tool that is able to quantify masking would come very useful, this analysis tool could also be useful for automating the process of masking minimization. To the authors knowledge, a measure of masking based on perceptual studies has not yet been proposed within the context of a mix. It is then the intention of this work to provide a meaningful quantitative measure of masking between the different tracks of a multi-track recording. The proposed measure is based on the widely accepted power spectrum model of masking [8]. The next

section presents each stage of the model in detail. The interaction between several common instruments (electric guitar, bass, synthesizer) is analyzed in section 3, and conclusions are presented in section 4.

2. THE CROSS-ADAPTIVE SIGNAL-TO-MASKER RATIO (SMR)

As mentioned before the main idea behind this work was to implement an analysis tool for audio engineers to be used when equalizing a multi-track recording in the attempt to spectrally unmask the different tracks. Additionally, given that the model is able to quantify masking, another possible application of the model is in a content-based equalization system. Such an equalizer falls under the category of Adaptive Audio Effects (A-DAFX) [9]. The main idea behind this type of effect is that the processing that takes place is controlled by sound features derived from the input sound over time. Additionally, a cross-adaptive effect is defined to be a type of A-DAFX that has multiple inputs/outputs and the individual processing of a single input is dependent on the content of all the inputs. This type of processing requires a feature extraction stage (analysis stage) that takes the interaction between all the inputs into account. Furthermore, because the aim of the equalization is to minimize unwanted masking, the analysis stage should be performed on a perceptual domain and based on psychoacoustic studies. The next section introduces such an analysis stage, namely, the cross-adaptive signal-to-masker ratio.

2.1 The Power Spectrum Model of Masking

A widely accepted model of masking has been proposed by Moore [8]. The model is based on many psychoacoustical experiments that have been carried out and improved in the past few decades [6]. Most of the steps of the cross-adaptive SMR explained below have been based on this model. Briefly, to calculate the amount of masking between two sounds, the excitation patterns for the two sounds are calculated. Then, the regions with significant excitation overlap in time and frequency are detected and finally a decision is made for each of these regions in which a sound is labeled as masker and the other one as maskee (the sound that is masked). The idea is that when minimizing unwanted masking, the sounds that are considered maskers in a given region are attenuated to achieve a desired signal-to-masker ratio expressed in decibels.

2.2 Outer/Middle Ear Filtering

The first step of the model is to transform the input sounds to a perceptual representation across frequency and time. For this we must first account for the transmission of sound through the outer and middle ear. Several experiments have helped to determine the transfer function of this filter [6]; it is depicted in figure 1. The filter shows a clear peak in the region around 3 kHz and significant attenuation to low and high frequencies. The filtering is performed in the frequency domain by multiplying the magnitude spectrum

Figure 1. Magnitude Response of the outer/middle ear filter. The filtering is applied in the frequency domain by multiplying the above response with the magnitude spectrum of each frame of audio.

of each frame of audio with the response shown in figure 1.

2.3 Excitation Pattern

The next step, after applying the outer/middle ear filtering is to calculate the excitation patterns of the analyzed sounds. The excitation pattern is meant to correspond to the average neural activity in response to a steady sound as a function of frequency [10]. It is calculated as the squared sum of the output (energy at the output) of each auditory filter described below as a function of the filters centre frequency. As such, the excitation pattern is a vector which contains the output energy of each of the 43 auditory filters of a frame of audio.

2.3.1 Auditory Filter Shape

Several experiments have been performed in order to estimate the shape of the auditory filters in the basilar membrane [8]. It has been concluded that the auditory filters take the form of a rounded exponential function. In addition it has been determined that the shape of these filters vary significantly with the level of the input sound it receives. Figure 2 illustrates this. Note that the lower frequency slope of the filter becomes less steep as the input level increases. This fact has a great implication in the case of music mixing. An engineer usually mixes a song in the 60 to 85 dB SPL range and this is also a reasonable range at which most people listen to music. This means that at this level the auditory filters in the cochlea take the corresponding form depicted in figure 2. This fact, together with the fact that the auditory filter bandwidths increase with center frequency, constitute what is known as the upward spread of masking. The upward spread of masking refers to the fact that low frequency sounds are more effective at masking higher frequency sounds. For this reason this model assumes that the music will be listened to at levels around 60-85 dB SPL, thus the auditory filters that are implemented are asymmetric, having an approximate

Figure 2. The response of the auditory filter has been found to change with input level. In the figure we can see the response of the auditory filter centered at 1KHz for different input levels ranging from 20 to 90 dB SPL. As you can see, the lower frequency slope becomes less steep with increasing input level.

shape to the one shown in figure 2 when the input level is 70 dB SPL.

2.3.2 Auditory Filter Bandwidths

The bandwidths of the auditory filters have also been found to change across frequency [6]. In this particular model the bandwidths are made to increase as a function of center frequency according to the Equivalent Rectangular Bandwidth scale:

$$ERB = 24.7(4.37F + 1) \quad (1)$$

Where F is frequency in kHz. This scale differs from the traditional Bark scale in that the bandwidths keep decreasing below 500 Hz [6]. Figure 3 shows the relationship between ERB band number and ERB bandwidth. In this model, the excitation pattern is calculated using 43 rounded exponential auditory filters spaced one ERB apart starting at $f_c = 50$ Hz.

2.3.3 The Excitogram

The last step in calculating the Excitation Pattern is simple. The energy at the output of each auditory filter is calculated as a function of the filters centre frequency and the resulting vector constitutes the excitation pattern at a given time. Additionally, because we are interested in the sounds temporal evolution we calculate an excitation pattern over time to form the excitogram [10]. Two example excitograms are depicted in figure 4 and figure 5. They were calculated with a window size of 46 ms and a hop size of 23 ms. The auditory filtering was applied in the frequency domain as a set of multiplications with the filters responses.

Figure 3. The relationship between the ERB band (1-43) and the auditory filter bandwidth at that band is shown in the figure.

Figure 4. The excitogram of a guitar strum (Am). It can be seen that higher frequencies decay faster than lower frequencies, this is an acoustic property of vibrating strings.

Figure 5. The excitogram of a sustained trumpet note (C3). It can be seen that this note is fairly stationary.

2.4 Masking Coefficient

The next step in the model is the calculation of the masking coefficient. This is a number between 0 and 1 that corresponds to the amount of effective excitation overlap between two sounds. The masking coefficient between two excitations is given by the following equation:

$$MC(t, b) = 1 - \left(\frac{|e_1(t, b) - e_2(t, b)|}{60dB} \right) \quad (2)$$

Where e_1 and e_2 are the matrices containing the excitograms of each sound in decibels. The absolute value of the difference between the excitations is normalized with respect to 60 dB and then subtracted from one. As a result, when the excitograms have a similar value for a given ERB band and time, the MC is close to one. This specific case would yield a low signal-to-masker ratio in that band, as the auditory filter gets a similar amount of energy from both sounds, so this means that both sounds are heavily competing to be heard. As this is the definition of masking we have adopted (see section 1.1) we call this descriptor the masking coefficient. In practice, all of the values of the excitations below a certain threshold th_{ex} were discarded in the computation of the Masking Coefficient; this was done to avoid having high MC values at regions where the excitation values were low because it is assumed that these components are masked by the louder components anyways. Also, the values of the MC which are less than a given threshold th_{mc} are set to zero as we believe they are not significant. The values of th_{mc} as well as th_{ex} were obtained experimentally, but they could be turned into user-controlled parameters. In the example above values of $th_{ex} = 20dB$ and $th_{mc} = 0.5$ were used. It is worth to analyze the MC descriptor depicted in figure 6. Basically, the MC descriptor above is saying that there is significant masking going on at the beginning of the sound (the first 5 seconds or so) and only in bands 1-28 approximately. If we look at the excitations of the sounds in the figures 4 and 5 we can see that the trumpet sound is longer than the guitar strum. This is why in figure 6 there is no masking detected after the sound of the strum has died off (around second 5). Also, as you may know, the high frequencies in a guitar strum tend to decay faster than the low frequencies; this means that the trumpet note and the guitar strum are no longer competing to be heard in the higher bands after the high frequencies of the strum have decayed. This can also be seen in figure 6.

2.5 The Cross Adaptive SMR

The last step in the model is the computation of the cross-adaptive signal-to-masker ratio. This means that a decision needs to be made in which one of the sounds is considered a masker and the other one a maskee in a given band and time. This is done because it well may be that a guitar sound can be masking (competing with) the bass in the lower bands, but it can be masked by the trumpet in the higher bands. In order to do this, the model makes use of two excitation descriptors, namely, the excitation centroid EC and the weighted average of the three most excited

Figure 6. The masking coefficient descriptor is a measure of the effective excitation overlap between two sounds. The figure above shows the MC between the guitar strum and sustained trumpet note of the examples above.

Figure 7. Descriptors EC (top) and EA (bottom) for the guitar strum.

auditory filters ERB band number (weighted by their excitation value), from now on EA . These descriptors are calculated in order to estimate the spectral region in which the sounds should live. For example, a bass should live well below a guitar and a guitar should live well below the cymbals, and these descriptors are able to give us this information. The masker/maskee estimation can be better illustrated with an example. In the case of the guitar strum sound ($s=1$) and trumpet note sound ($s=2$) both descriptors are calculated for both sounds. Figure 7 and figure 8 show the calculated descriptors for both sounds. Based on these

descriptors a decision is made like follows. For each of the time/frequency regions where the MC reveals masking the following distances are calculated:

$$\Delta c_s = |b_t - EC_{t,s}| \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta c3_s = |b_t - EA_{t,s}| \quad (4)$$

Where b_t is the band where masking was detected (by the MC descriptor) at a given time t . $EC_{t,s}$ is the excitation

Figure 8. Descriptors EC (top) and EA (bottom) for the sustained trumpet note.

centroid of track s at time t . From these values ($\Delta c_1, \Delta c_2$) we can figure out if the spectral region in which the sounds were competing is closer to the centroid of either sound, which we are assuming is the region around which the sound should live. Therefore, the sound responsible for the smallest value of Δ (either using equation 3 or 4) is considered to be the maskee (the sound that is being masked), and the other sound is considered the masker. It has been determined that the descriptors mentioned above behave differently depending on the sound. Sometimes the centroid is smoother and sometimes the 3-peak average ERB value is smoother. The pros and cons of using either descriptor for the analysis are still under investigation but as an initial suggestion, the descriptor that shows the smoothest evolution should be chosen. An example of such decision using only the centroid (only using equation 3) is depicted in figure 9. The red regions corresponds to the regions where the trumpet is considered a maskee, the green region corresponds to the regions where the guitar is considered a maskee. In the region where a sound is considered a maskee the sound is protected in the sense that in order to increase the signal-to-masker ratio, the other sound will be attenuated in that band. In this specific case, the sound of the guitar in the higher bands was protected at the beginning of the sound, but once the higher frequencies decayed, the guitar was assigned to the lower bands and the trumpet was assigned to the higher bands. This demonstrates the ability of the system to dynamically adapt to the relationship between the two sounds. Apart from being able to allocate a portion of the spectrum to each sound, the proposed model is also able to quantify the amount of masking between the tracks, this means that an audio engineer could keep track of exact values that work for given situations. To quantify the amount of masking we calculate the SMR which is explained next.

Finally, now that the sounds have been labeled as masker/maskee, it is possible to calculate the signal-to-masker ratio at any auditory filter at any point in time. The SMR is then given by:

$$SMR_{t,b} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{E_{s_{t,b}}}{E_{m_{t,b}}} \right) \quad (5)$$

Figure 9. The masker/maskee decision for the guitar strum and sustained trumpet note. It can be seen that the decision dynamically adapts the content of both sounds. In this case, equation 3 is responsible for the decision.

Figure 10. Instantaneous SMR for guitar strum and sustained trumpet note. The decision function is responsible for labeling the sound as masker (Em) or maskee (Es).

Where E_s is the excitation of the maskee (protected signal) at time t and band b , and E_m is the excitation of the masker at time t and band b . This is the measure that is used to quantify masking between the different instruments, it is expressed in decibels. An example of the SMR measure for a frame (around second 0.75) of the sounds above is depicted in figure 10. As you can see, the SMR does not have a value for some bands; this means that the MC did not detect any masking in those areas. The MC used to calculate the above SMR was calculated with a $th_{mc} = 0.8$ which means that only areas with a high degree of excitation overlapping are considered. The SMR can have both positive and negative values, a value close to 0 indicates a similar amount of energy of both sounds in that auditory filter. A positive increasing value indicates less masking (less competition) and a negative value indicates more masking (the energy of the masker is higher in that auditory filter, so there is more competition). To summarize, the whole process of calculating the cross-adaptive SMR is made up of four fundamental blocks. The first step is to calculate the excitations of the input tracks by first filtering each input track with the outer/middle ear filter, then

Figure 11. Overview of cross-adaptive SMR computation.

passing them through an auditory filter-bank and summing the squared energy of each filter's output as a function of the filters centre frequency. Then, the masking coefficient is calculated using equation 2. Then, in order to label the tracks as either masker or maskee, both the excitation centroid (EC) and the MC descriptor are used in equation 3, or alternatively, the 3-peak excitation centroid (EA) and the MC descriptor are used in equation 4. Once the sounds are labelled across frequency and time (see figure 9) it is possible to use equation 5 to obtain the SMR. Remember that the auditory filter-bank is made up of 43 rounded exponential filters, each spaced one ERB apart (equation 1), with the first filter at $f_c = 50$ Hz.

3. ANALYSIS OF COMMON INSTRUMENTS

This section is concerned with the analysis of the proposed model. Four common instruments of a multi-track recording are selected, namely the bass, rhythm electric guitar 1 (playing chords), synthesizer, and electric guitar 2 (playing arpeggios an octave above the chords). We will see how these tracks mask each other across frequency and time in a song excerpt of length 9 seconds. The analysis is done with a graphical user interface that allows setting the relative levels of the tracks before they are analyzed. This is very important as the relative levels between tracks dictate the amount of masking between them. The tracks are set to the same relative levels for all cases (or very similar), the idea is to investigate their interaction. The first case to be explored is the bass. Figure 12 shows the result of the analysis between the bass and the rest of the tracks. The regions where the bass is masked are shown in green. As you

Figure 12. Top: bass and electric guitar 1. Middle: bass and synth. Bottom: bass and electric guitar 2.

can see, in all of the cases the bass was found to be masked in the lower bands, this agrees with intuition as it is known that the bass guitar should be the dominant instrument in the lower ranges. In this specific case, the instrument that seems to be interfering the most with the bass is the synthesizer, and the instrument that interferes the least with the bass, is the electric guitar 2. Following is the analysis of the rhythm electric guitar 1. The images below show the results of the analysis between the guitar and the rest of the tracks. The regions where the electric guitar 1 is masked are shown in green, and the regions where the electric guitar is masking another sound are shown in red. As you can observe, the electric guitar 1 is masking more bands of other sounds than the bass did. Also, the instrument that seems to mask the electric guitar 1 the most is the electric guitar 2, followed by the synthesizer. An interesting fact to observe is that the electric guitar 2 is masking the electric guitar 1 in band 10, but the synth is not (at least for most of the time). All of these subtle details can be useful to an audio engineer when equalizing the sounds.

Next we will observe the interaction between the synthesizer and the rest of the sounds. Figure 13 shows the results of the analysis between the synth and the rest of the sounds. In the case of the synth we can observe that the only instrument that is masked by the synth in the lower bands is the bass. Also, the electric guitars both show a similar interaction with the synth, although electric guitar 1 seems to be interfering with the synth in lower bands. From the visualization of these results it is possible to make some conclusions once the interaction between all tracks has been analyzed. First of all, the bass track was

Figure 13. Top: electric guitar1 and bass. Middle: electric guitar1 and synth. Bottom: electric guitar1 and electric guitar 2.

Figure 14. Top: synth and bass. Middle: synth and electric guitar1. Bottom: synth and electric guitar 2.

determined to be masked in the lower bands for all cases, this means that this instrument should definitively occupy the lower bands and the rest of the tracks should be attenuated at those bands to increase the signal-to-masker ratio of the bass in a given region. Secondly, The rhythm electric guitar 1 was masked below band 5 and above band 10 by the electric guitar 2 and it was masked only above band 10 by the synth, this implies that the electric guitar 2 should live higher in frequency than the electric guitar 1, which in turn should live higher in frequency than the synthesizer.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A quantitative measure of masking between the different tracks of a multi-track recording has been implemented. We have seen that the model is able to decide if an instrument is acting as a masker or as a maskee in a time/frequency representation by means of analyzing its spectral content. This decision has been analyzed with several common instrument tracks and we have shown that the model is able to allocate a portion of the spectrum to each instrument, which is a task that most audio engineers need to develop a skill for. Furthermore, once the decision has been made we can calculate the SMR for any band at any point in time where masking is detected which means that masking can be quantified. Also, the visualization of this decision can be very useful for audio engineers when equalizing tracks to reduce masking, which is known to be an important task in music post-production [7]. Furthermore, the proposed model could also be used as the analysis stage of an adaptive audio effect in the future that could automate the masking minimization process, although this matter is still under investigation.

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